

NBSINFRA

Funded by the
European Union

City lab Booklet

Ruse
Bulgaria

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All the City Labs

The **NBSINFRA** project has **five city labs across Europe** that are assessing **how cities can handle different challenges and stay resilient through Nature-Based Solutions**. Each city lab aims to investigate how NBS can protect local infrastructure, preserve biodiversity, restore ecosystems and confront the challenges of climate change. The goal is to deliver tailored solutions and risk indicators for specific locations, contribute to city contingency plans and **increase the resilience and sustainability of NBS for future generations**.

Nature Based Solutions stages across City Labs

1	(Co-) Diagnosis and (Co-) Characterization Collaborative assessment of the current conditions and identification of key challenges and opportunities.
2	(Co-) Design and (Co-) Creation Co-designing and co-creating nature-based solutions with input from diverse stakeholders.
3	(Co-) Implementation Collaborative implementation of the solutions, ensuring active participation from all involved parties.
4	(Co-) Evaluation and (Co-) Monitoring Ongoing evaluation and monitoring of the solutions effectiveness through collective input and feedback.
5	(Co-) Amplification or (Co-) Replication Expanding or replicating the solutions collaboratively to ensure broader impact and scalability.

Ruse
Bulgaria

NBS stages: 1

Fingal
Ireland

NBS stages: 1-2

Aveiro
Portugal

NBS stages: 1-2

Prague
Czechia

NBS stages: 3-4

Cologne
Germany

NBS stages: 4

Visit our website for a more accurate insight on the project's city labs

www.nbsinfra.eu

Ruse

Bulgaria

Historical/Cultural context

Ruse is a NBSINFRA project partner – City Lab, supported by ASDE-ECOREGIONS. The municipality of Ruse is an economic, transport, cultural and educational center of regional, national and trans-border importance, located on the Danube River, on the border between Bulgaria and Romania.

Fig. 1. Scheme of state policy in the field of disaster protection

Ruse is the biggest Bulgarian city on the Danube River and the most significant transport, logistics, business and cultural centre of North Bulgaria. The number of the population is 150 000. 23 centuries ago, an ancient Thracian port marked the beginning of the town. In the late 1st century, the Roman fortress of Sexaginta Prista

(from Latin “port for 60 ships”) became part of the Roman Danube Limes, the northern frontier of the empire. Ruse is a port on the Danube, where cultural traces from the West and the East, from the North and the South have landed and got rooted. Visit the [link](#) for more information

Important Note: More information on Ruse environment, economics, infrastructure, climate, etc. in the Ruse Detailed Report prepared by ASDE-ECOREGIONS with the support of Ruse Municipality specialists, plus external experts (NBSINFRA GOOGLE-DRIVE).

Basics: The National Disaster Risk Reduction Strategy defines the goals in Bulgaria. The state administration forms and implements the state policy in risk protection. The Association of the Bulgaria Municipalities (NSDR) leads the disaster protection plans (fig.1).

RUSE Master Plan/Networks

Ruse Municipality is managed in correspondence with a mandatory Master Plan (fig.2). In the [Ruse Detailed Report](#) is presented detailed information on: In the Natural environment, Construction, Power supply, Water supply (fig.3.), Water potential of the area, Road and Railway infrastructure (fig.4), Water and Air transport, Building fund, etc.).

Fig.2 Master Plan of Ruse Municipality

Fig. 3. Water supply network (Ruse Master Plan)

Fig.4. Ruse Municipal Transport network.

Hazards/risks - analysis

Possible disasters that may occur in Ruse are: 1.Natural Disasters- earthquakes, floods, snowfall, landslides, etc.; 2.Disasters as a result of human/industrial accidents;3. Disasters as consequences of transport accidents; 4.Disasters from epidemics and pandemics; Earthquakes (fig. 5); Floods (fig.6); Snowstorms/snowfalls and icing (fig. 7); Landslides ; Other risks- not listed for NBSINFRA;

Fig.5. Proposal for a normative earthquake risk map for a recurrence period of 475 years and average shear-wave velocity in the upper 30 m of the soil/rock profile for the city of Ruse

Fig. 6. Map of the Bulgarian Danube districts/Regions with significant potential risk of flooding (RSPRF) and Rusenski Lom Catchment area.

Fig. 7. Problematic roads during snowfall.

More information on hazards / risk assessment in [Ruse Detailed Report](#)

LOCAL EXPOSURE/LOSS Data sets/ RiskMan system

Integration of EO(COPERNICUS/SENTINEL 2 data) and in-situ data is essential. Application of ISO standard on LC/LU classification, integrated legally accepted urban management elements from the Master Plan are mandatory (see Ruse Detailed Report). Risk assessment is part of the management process. Under discussion are two approaches – one is traditional, based on standard BG ISO 31000.

After carrying out the risk analysis, the Ruse municipality decided on the limit and the levels of risk with the following levels: “Moderate”, “High” and “Extreme”. These are plotted in Table 4.

Table 4. Template for disaster risk assessment on the territory of Ruse

No.	Hazard Identification	Risk analysis			Service risks					Risk assessment					TOTAL	
		Probability	Consequence	Risk Level	Social Consequences	Infrastructure Core Damages	Economic Losses	Administrative Consequences	Outcome /Result	Prevention	Preparedness	Response	Recovery	Adaptation /Mitig.		Growth Level Assessment
1	Earthquakes Chemical pollution related to industrial accidents and road accidents.	Probably	Moderate	High	3	4	4	2	5,0	3	3	3	4	3,25	3	15,9
2		Probably	Large	High	3	3	3	3	6	3	3	3	4	3,25	4	12,3
3	Human pandemics	Possible	Catastrophic	High	3	1	4	3	6,8	4	4	4	4	4	1	11,9
4	Floods	Probably	Moderate	High	3	3	3	3	6,0	3	3	2	3	2,75	3	11,8
5	Strong storms	Very likely	Moderate	High	2	3	2	2	4,5	4	3	3	4	3,5	3	11,0
6	Snowstorms and icing	Very likely	Small	Moderate y	2	3	2	1	4,5	4	4	4	4	4	2	10,5
7	Radiocesium contamination	Possible	Moderate	Moderate y	2	1	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	3,25	3	10,8
8	Landslides	Possible	Small	Moderate y	2	1	1	1	3,5	3	3	3	4	3,25	3	9,5
9	Forest and field fires	Very likely	Small	Moderate y	2	2	2	3	4,2	2	3	2	3	2,5	3	9,2
10	Ice block on the Danube river	Probably	Small	Moderate y	1	2	2	3	3,2	4	4	3	4	4,25	2	9,5
11	Contagious animal diseases	Probably	Moderate	High	2	3	3	3	4	2	3	3	4	3	2	9,0
12	Fire in urbanized areas	Very likely	Moderate	High	2	3	1	1	4	2	2	1	2	1,75	3	8,5
13	Oil spill along the Danube	Possible	Small	Moderate y	1	2	1	4	3,4	2	2	2	4	2,5	2	7,6

Site selection and Risk Prevention

Principles/criteria for reducing risk through prevention

The Municipal Council for Disaster Risk Reduction and other state and local structures, plan and implement preventive measures as: analysis, forecast; development of the Municipal Disaster Protection Plan (MDP); measures for conducting exercises; education and training; planning of evacuation, medical provision.

Prevention the main risk –flooding/Selection of site

According to the Flood Risk Management Plan (FRM) in the Danube Region of Basin Management, the lands along the river Rusenski Lom are with a significant risk of flooding (RZPRN and PURN). Risk Maps are prepared. A simulation model of a dam high wave was also developed. Floods risks measures are listed in the Ruse Detailed Report.

Sites selection

Monitoring mitigation effects on NBS

Fig.9 Ruse City Lab-test areas

In general the selected pilot sites under the NBSINFRA project for Ruse Municipality are:

- **Ruse-Giurgiu Danube bridge – Site A**
- **Rusenski Lom - Site B - Ruse Danube River port ; Rusenski Lom River, Monitoring, Exposure & Loss Dataset; ISO 19144-2 application, local sensors network, NBS, AI flood risk preventive tool**
- **Trans-border infrastructure - TEN-T European highway; Monitoring, Exposure & Loss Dataset; ISO 19144-2; local sensors network- NBS and other services to be discussed**

Priority case Rusenski Lom River –Site B

We have selected a most vulnerable site – the lower course of the river R. Lom/Ruse Quarry and its confluence with the Danube – Pilot Site B.

Rusenski Lom - In 2008 was realised the restoration of dykes of the correction of the Rusenski Lom River from km.3+000 to km.15+500; allowing high waters.

Previous flooding made it necessary to upgrade the dikes in 2015-16 – fig. 10. to fig. 13

Fig. 10. The section below the “Prista” hut (flooded at high levels).

Fig. 11. The rails of the West port flooded at a level of 764 cm.

Fig. 12. Rusenski Lom River length of the corrected section-12 km.

Fig. 13. Agricultural lands flooded by groundwater at high levels.

Potentially dangerous dam in which accidents can occur:

Dam “Nikolovo”-1,270,000m³, potentially dangerous (fig. 14.); ASDE, with support from Ruse Municipality, has developed an assessment of Dam Nikolovo, including a 3D simulation.

Fig. 14. Dam Nikolovo.

Preliminary assessment-risk of floods along rivers and dams

Based on Water Act and Dir. 2007/60/EU, preliminary analysis of the risk of rivers floods in Bulgaria was prepared. Parallel, ASDE, with local experts, realised a package of user-friendly models on Rusenski Lom. Under NBSINFRA project, an upgrading is provided.

Characteristic floods of the Ruse territory: 1. River overflows; 2. Torrential rains; 3. Accidents/bad management; 4. Neg. Actions. Flash floods in urban areas - street pavements create conditions for high water velocities, concentration and no losses from soil infiltration. A similar effect occurs in land with a significant slope of the bottom and cliffs. Man-made Floods accidents on hydro tech. facilities/ accidents, bad management, no-maintained riverbed.

NBS Measures/Factors that reduce risk

Measures to reduce/prevent floods caused by man-made factors:

1. Continuous quality control of the built facilities along the rivers
2. Control of riverbeds, dikes, bridges, culverts
3. Permanent control on dam walls, spillways, discharge facilities
4. Continuous surveillance/early warning, based on:
 - 4.1. Information/data provided by individuals, organisations, etc.
 - 4.2. Information/ data from meteorological, hydrological, monitoring systems
 - 4.3. Prognostic information
 - 4.4. International data exchange

ASDE, in collaboration with the Ruse Municipality Ruse, proposed:

1. Monitoring of changes (COPERNICUS/SENTINEL data/ services)
2. Manual/AI-based algorithm on mandatory planned indexes for greenery, building, etc.
3. LC/LU using ISO 19144-2 (LCMCL)
4. Simulation risk modelling
5. A network of flood sensors (ACWA)
6. Web-based Exposure and Loss dataset
7. Other NBS tools (NBSINFRA partners)

Strategy–Start-with Pilot Site–B, later Ruse municipality.
Additional application for Sites A,B,C - RiskMan automatic tool on risk prevention; Other applications, depending on the stakeholder request and project capacity.

Planned action for pilot site B

- Monitoring of changes – trends in mandatory NB indexes
- ACWA Rusenski Lom network (sensors, server, database)
- Resilience in cultural heritage zones- Ivanovo Rock churches
- Upgrading flood models - critical infrastructure& assets
- Assessment of the new TEN-T road, crossing Rusenski Lom

Example-Innovative approach to monitoring of changes – ASDE team and external experts

Extracted data, from two Sentinel-2 tiles: 35TLJ N 35THM. The time series covers 7 years (2017 till 2023). The processing workflow is based on the CAP Checks by Monitoring (CbM) approach, providing trends according the risk prevention concept, uniting EO+in-situ data.AI algorithms will be applied when needed. Main mandatory indexes (Master Plan) to be assessed:

- Trends - changes of potentially available urban green space
- Comparisons of the potentially available urban green space
- Max % of built buildings of city infrastructure (sealed land)

Target monitoring of changes using – 1. COPERNICUS /SENTINEL services; 2. AI algorithm for automatic analysis of indexes; 3. Mandatory management of territorial elements according trends.

Examples below: The digital map of trends is a result of applying the mechanism of CbM under best European / global practices. The results show the trends of maintaining, increasing or decreasing the percentage of the free greening area - one of the main indices for the mandatory “functional zones” under the Ruse Master Plan. Mainly urbanised territories are studied – agri- or forest and natural environment are subject to different methodology. A special interest will be given to the UNESCO areas – “the Rock churches”.

The intermediate result of monitoring approach - fig. 15, 16, 17.

Fig. 15. Map –“Green indicators tendencies” 2017-2023.

Map of trends in the percentage of potentially green areas in the functional zones of urbanized territories in the municipality of Ruse (period 2017-2023)

Fig. 16. “Green” areas tendencies in Ruse Municipality for 2017-2023.

Analysis of trends in the period 2017-2023

Fig. 17. Map –“Green indicators tendencies” 2017-2023.

Orange outline: Negative trend observed in potential green spaces

Blue outline: No such negative trend observed

This trend is important as it shows partial non-compliance with the mandatory Ruse Master Plan indicators

Key activities

Completed activities

- LC/LU classification under ISO 19144-2
- Semi manual/AI assessment of mandatory MP indexes (green)
- Actualization of simulation floods for Rusenski Lom river

Future activities

- Floods Simulation modelling (to be discussed)
- ACWA sensors network (under tendering procedure)
- Exposure and Loss data information system (to be installed)
- Cultural sites (Nikolovo rock churches and Basarbovo area)
- Discussed action- SAR monitoring of land subsistence

Best practices

- Innovative LC/LU classification -based on ISO 19144-2(LCML)
- Check by Monitoring on mandatory indexes, using semi manual/AI algorithms
- User targeted approach
- Applying JRC/GOOGLE- water bodies service
- Applying EU services and platforms, as example -Using vegetation phenology data is derived from SENTINEL-2 - (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service -as HP-VPP product

“Nature-based Solutions address societal challenges through actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified ecosystems, benefiting people and nature at the same time. They target major challenges like climate change, disaster risk reduction, food and water security, biodiversity loss and human health, and are critical to sustainable development.”

International Union for Conservation of Nature

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